

Effect of Substituents on the Course of Cyclization of Polycarboxylic Esters

Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture for 1968*

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At the outset I would like to thank once again the Indian Chemical Society for appointing me as the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecturer for 1968. I have chosen the subject of my second lecture on the basis of my experiences in the line which I took up as a beginner in research during the last few years of Acharya Ray. As I was working in those days in Professor J. C. Bardhan's laboratory, which was practically below the living room of Acharya Ray in the University College of Science, Calcutta, I could feel all the time that this great man was over me.

Before I pass on to the actual subject, I would prefer to place a summary of the over all position, and it may be considered on the basis of the condition prevailing thirty years back from now. In view of my interest in undertaking synthetic work on steroids, I was fascinated by the course of Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I) as established by Baker¹ in connection with his proposed synthetic work in bile acid group. The above findings were utilized by Banerjee² in connection with his synthetic work in the field of bile acids and sex hormones. Nevertheless, it was found desirable to check up the basic findings of Baker with regard to the course of cyclization of the above tricarboxylic ester (I) by application of more convincing tests before actually undertaking application of these findings in my desired project on the synthesis of steroids. As a result, it was found that the course of the cyclization was just opposite to that established by Baker and the product synthesized by Banerjee on the basis of Baker's postulation was actually found to have a structure different from that required by Banerjee. Similarly, difficulties and paradoxical cases observed by various other synthetic workers in the field of steroids and terpenoids could be clarified and useful generalizations arrived at regarding the course of cyclization of polycarboxylic esters. It was also possible to study the comparative position with regard to the positive character of an alkyl group and the negative character of a carboalkoxy group.

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1. J. W. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1548.
2. D. K. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 423.

* Second lecture.

An excellent example of Dieckmann cyclization of an unsymmetrical polycarboxylic ester is provided by that of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I). It has two possibilities for cyclization giving the cyclopentanone esters (II) and/or (III). This cyclization was first studied by Ruzicka³ in connection with his synthesis of fenchone, but as he was interested only in the hydrolysed keto-acid (IV) it was not necessary for him to establish the correct structure of the cyclized product as (II) or (III).

Baker¹, in connection with his synthetic work in the field of bile-acids, observed that on careful oxidation of the Dieckmann cyclization product of (I), α -methylglutaric acid, a liquid acid analysis of the silver salt of which corresponded with that of α -hydroxy- α -methylglutaric acid and a trace of succinic acid could be obtained, and on this basis he represented the cyclized product as ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-2,3-dicarboxylate (II). No trace of β -methyl-tricarballic acid or of methylsuccinic acid, the products expected by him from oxidation of an ester of structure (III), could be detected. Later Banerjee², also interested in synthetic work in the field of bile-acids and sex hormones, condensed ethyl β -chloropropionate with sodio-derivative of the Dieckmann cyclization product of (I) and after successive hydrolysis, Clemmensen reduction and esterification of the product, followed by a second Dieckmann cyclization and hydrolysis, obtained a product which was stated to be the bicyclic ketone (V) on the basis of Baker's findings. The nitric acid oxidation product of (V) was described as impure (because of somewhat lower m.p. than that described in the

3. L. Ruzicka, *Ber. deutsch. chem. Ges.*, 1917, 50, 1362.

literature⁴) *trans*-1-methylcyclopentane-2-acetic-1-carboxylic acid (VI) and this further supported the findings of Baker, although the mixed m.p. with authentic specimen was not compared.

Two other interesting cases of cyclization of polycarboxylic esters studied upto 1940 may be cited in this connection, e.g., those of ethyl 2,2-dimethylbutane-1,3,4-tricarboxylate (IX) by Perkin and Thrope⁵ and ethyl butane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (XII) by Kay and Perkin⁶ and by Ruzicka, Borges de Almeida and Brack⁷. In the former case, the cyclization leads to the keto-ester (X) and not the keto-ester (XI). In the latter case, the cyclization proceeds with the formation of the two isomeric keto-esters (XIII) and (XIV) in which (XIII) largely predominates. Considering the keto-esters (II), (X) and (XIII) as derivatives of succinic ester, and the keto-esters (III), (XI) and (XIV) as derivatives of glutaric ester, it appeared at this stage that in such cyclizations whenever there was a possibility for the formation of the succinic ester type and the glutaric ester type, the former is formed by preference, as all the cases cited above conform to this generalization.

4. K. D. Errington and R. P. Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 668.

J. W. Barret, A. H. Cook and R. P. Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1068.

5. W. H. Perkin Jr. and J. F. Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 85, 778.

6. F. W. Kay and W. H. Perkin Jr., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 85, 1645.

7. L. Ruzicka, A. Borges de Almeida and A. Brack, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1934, 17, 183.

In spite of the above apparently balanced position, a critical study of the Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I) was later undertaken by Chakravarti⁸⁻¹² based on direct comparison of products with authentic specimens. In the first instance, ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I) was cyclized with finely divided sodium and the product was alkylated *in situ* with methyl and ethyl iodides in separate experiments (Chart I). In each case, the structure of the alkylated cyclized ester (XV) and/or (XVI) was established by ketonic hydrolysis to the corresponding keto-acid (XVII) and/or (XVIII) as also by acid hydrolysis to the corresponding tribasic acid (XIX) and/or (XX). For the purpose of direct comparison, authentic specimens of the keto-acids (XVII; R = Me, Et) and (XVIII; R = Me, Et), and the tricarboxylic acids (XIX; R = Me, Et) and (XX; R = Me, Et) were synthesized by unambiguous methods (Chart II). On the basis of the results obtained it was established beyond doubt that contrary to the observations of Baker¹ and Banerjee² the sodium condensation of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I) leads to ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-3,5-dicarboxylate (III) and not ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-2,3-dicarboxylate (II). It was also observed (Chart III) by Chakravarti¹² that the ester (I) on Dieckmann cyclization followed by reduction with

8. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 173.
9. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 189.
10. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 243.
11. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 247.
12. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 399.

sodium amalgam to the corresponding hydroxy acid and then on dehydration and hydrogenation gave *cis*-1-methylcyclopentane-1,3-dicarboxylic acid (XXI) and not 1-methylcyclopentane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (XXII) (cf. Datta¹³ for the unsaturated acid) the expected product on the basis of the postulations of Baker¹.

Chart II

In view of the above position with regard to the Dieckmann cyclization of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I), it is evident that the bicyclic ketone obtained by Banerjee² should be represented by (VIII) and not by (V), and the acid obtained from it by nitric acid oxidation by (VII) and not (VI). This was confirmed by Chakravarti¹¹ by comparison with authentic specimens synthesized for the purpose.

In connection with studies on camphorquinone rearrangement, it was observed by Chakravarti¹⁴⁻¹⁷ that cyclization of ethyl 2-methylpentane-1,3,5-tricarboxylate (XXIII) yields the keto-ester (XXIV) and not (XXV), as on methylation followed by hydrolysis it

13. P. C. Datta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 611.
14. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 301.
15. R. N. Chakravarti, *Current Science*, 1944, 13, 158.
16. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 319.
17. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 322.

yielded the keto-acid (XXVI). No trace of the isomeric keto-acid, 2,3-dimethylcyclohexan-1-one-4-carboxylic acid (XXVII), which was previously obtained by Chakravarti¹⁸ by re-arrangement of santenonequinone, could be found in the final product of hydrolysis. In

this case also, the keto-acid was identified by direct comparison with authentic specimens of the two isomeric keto-acids, (XXVI) and (XXVII), synthesized for the purpose by unambiguous methods (Chart IV).

In connection with another work, the course of cyclization of ethyl β,β -dimethyladipate (XXVIII) with sodium was also critically investigated by Chakravarti¹⁸. In this case (Chart V), as is evident, the two possibilities are formation of (XXIX) and (XXX). On methylation of the product of cyclization and subsequent hydrolysis only 2,4,4-trimethylcyclopentanone (XXXI) could be obtained. The liquid ketone and its semicarbazone were found to be identical with the corresponding products obtained by unambiguous methods by previous workers¹⁹⁻²². From a comparison of the boiling points of the ketones and the

18. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1028.

19. O. Wallach, *Annalen der Chemie*, 1918, 414, 331.

20. A. N. Dey and R. P. Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1063.

21. J. R. N. van Kregten, *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas.*, 1916, 36, 78.

22. W. A. Noyes, *Ber. deutsch. chem. Ges.*, 1899, 32, 2291.

It is evident from the above results that the methyl (Me) groups in (I), (IX), (XXIII) and (XXVIII) exert some kind of steric influence (cf. Chakravarti^{18,23}) on the reactive methylene groups marked (*) whereby these are made less reactive as compared to the methylene groups at the other end of the chain. This effect appears to be due to the positive character of the methyl group. The reactivity of a methylene group depends on the ionizability of the hydrogen atoms as positively charged hydrogen ions. This requires an electron acceptor. The methyl group has got the tendency of releasing electron rather than accepting it and by its closer proximity it deactivates a reactive methylene group. Considering the course of Dieckmann cyclization in the cases cited above, it may be concluded that the action of sodium on the ester of a β -alkyl-adipic or-pimelic acid, having two alternatives for cyclization, may be expected to lead to a ketonic ester in which the reactive methylene group nearer to the alkyl radical remains unaffected by preference. The other isomer in such a case, if produced at all, can only be in much smaller amount. This view is also in line with the results obtained by the cyclization of ethyl β -methyladipate²⁴ and ethyl β -methylpimelate²⁵.

Similar to the deactivating influence of the methyl group, the carbethoxy group with electron accepting properties may activate a methylene in the α -position and this activating influence may be to a somewhat less extent relayed to a methylene group in the β -position. As an example for the activating influence of a carbethoxy group on the β -methylene group, the cyclization of ethyl butane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (XII) may be cited. As mentioned above, the cyclization proceeds with the formation of a mixture of the two isomeric keto-esters (XIII) and (XIV) in which (XIII) largely predominates. Introduction of two methyl groups in the 3-position of (XII), as in ethyl 2,2-dimethylbutane-1,3,4-tricarboxylate (IX) results in formation of only (X) during cyclization with sodium. Evidently, the negative carbethoxy group attached to the β -carbon atom in (XII) has got more activating influence on the α -methylene group than on the δ -methylene group, with the result that more of (XIII) is formed than (XIV) in the Dieckmann cyclization of (XII).

It may be noted, however, that the activating influence of the carbethoxy group is much less than the deactivating influence of the methyl group, since in the case of (XII) considerable quantities of the other isomer (XIV) is also produced, whereas in all the examples studied with methyl group, e.g., cyclization of (I), (IX), (XXIII) and (XXVIII), only one isomer could be isolated. It appears from these findings that the positive character of the methyl group is quantitatively greater than the negative character of the carbethoxy group. This is also borne out by the results of cyclization of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I) in which a methyl group and a carbethoxy group are attached to the same carbon atom in the appropriate position.

23. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. and Proc. Inst. Chemists (India)*, 1961, 33, 261.

24. W. Dieckmann and A. Groeneveld, *Ber. deutsch. chem. Ges.*, 1900, 33, 595.

25. A. Einhorn and L. Klages, *Ber. deutsch. chem. Ges.*, 1901, 34, 3793.

It is interesting to refer to the unsuccessful attempt made by Goldberg, Hunziker, Billeter and Rosenberg²⁶ for the synthesis of 1-methylbicyclo-(3.4.0)-nonane-5,9-dione (XXXVII) in connection with their synthetic work in the field steroids and sex hormones. It was expected that the cyclization of ethyl 2-methyl-pentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (XXXIII) would lead to ethyl 3-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2,3-dicarboxylate (XXXIV), which on condensation with ethyl β -chloropropionate followed by hydrolysis and esterification would produce the keto-ester (XXXIVa). The latter after a second cyclization with sodium followed by hydrolysis would yield the desired 1-methylbicyclo-(3.4.0)-nonane-5,9-dione (XXXVII) (Chart VI).

It is evident that ethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (XXXIII) may cyclize in either of three ways giving the keto-esters (XXXIV), (XXXV) and (XXXVI). The

β -carbon atom in (XXXIII) is substituted by a methyl group as well as a carboxy group. In view of the conclusion as drawn above with regard to the greater deactivating influence of the methyl group as compared to the activating influence of the carboxy group, it may be inferred that the ϵ -methyl group in (XXXIII) is far more reactive than the α -methylene group which is adjacent to the methyl group. Accordingly, the cyclization of ethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (XXXIII) may be expected to yield (XXXV) and/or (XXXVI) but not (XXXIV) contrary to the expectation of Goldberg *et al.* Consequently, the cyclized ester after condensation with ethyl β -chloropropionate followed by hydrolysis and esterification would yield the keto-esters (XXXVa) and/or (XXXVIa) instead of (XXXIVa). The reason for failure of the Swiss chemists to cyclize their product

26. M. W. Goldberg, F. Hunziker, J. R. Billeter and H. R. Rosenberg, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, 30, 200.

is thus quite clear (cf. Chakravarti²⁷). The keto-esters (XXXVa) and (XXXVIa) are not suitable for Dieckmann cyclization, since this cyclization requires the presence, in the starting material, of two ester groupings separated by a chain of four or five carbon atoms. In the above cyclization of (XXXIII) N. K. Chakravarty and Banerjee²⁸ could isolate after hydrolysis a cyclopentanone acid corresponding to (XXXVI), but the yield is not mentioned.

In this connection, the extremely interesting and anomalous case of the cyclization of ethyl pentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (XXXVIII) may be cited. Its structure bears the same relation to ethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (XXXIII) as ethyl butane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (XII) to ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I). The tricarboxylic ester (XXXVIII) has got three alternatives for cyclization leading to formation of the keto-esters (XXXIX), (XL) and (XLI) (Chart VII). On the basis of the findings with regard to the cyclization of ethyl butane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (XII), the product of cyclization in this case should be expected to consist mainly of the cyclohexanone ester (XXXIX), which is formed through the reactive methylene group at the α -position, along with a much smaller proportion of a mixture of the cyclopentanone ester (XLI) and the other isomeric cyclohexanone ester (XL), both formed through the ϵ -methylene group. This reaction was first carried out by Perkin and his collaborators²⁹, who obtained γ -keto-hexahydrobenzoic acid (XLII) and not the cyclopentanone acid (XLIII) by hydrolysis of the mixed cyclized product. This is in agreement with the above, since in the mixed product of cyclization the cyclohexanone ester (XXXIX) is the major constituent, and of the remainder, consisting of the isomeric cyclohexanone ester (XL) and the cyclopentanone ester (XLI), (XL) also yields γ -keto-hexahydrobenzoic acid (XLII) by hydrolysis.

27. R. N. Chakravarti, *Experientia*, 1947, 3, 149.

28. N. K. Chakravarty and D. K. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 377.

29. M. E. Dobson, J. Ferns and W. H. Perkin Jr., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 2010.

Later, Chatterjee, Das and Barpujari³⁰ observed that ethyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate (XLIV) on boiling in an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide was transformed into ethyl 5-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (XLI). According to the opinion of these workers, the transformation takes place through the tricarboxylic ester (XXXVIII), which on the basis of the experimental results recorded by Perkin and his collaborators should afford ethylcyclohexan-1-one-2,3-dicarboxylate (XXXIX) by cyclization. In view of these anomalous results, N. K. Chakravarti and Banerjee²⁸ repeated the experiments of both groups of workers and were, in the end, confused to find that both sides stated their experimental facts correctly. In the opinion of Chakravarti³¹ (XLI) obtained by Chatterjee and his collaborators³⁰ was formed through an ester anion of (XXXVIII). Sen and Bagchi³², in connection with their work on synthesis of diterpenoid resin acids corroborated the prediction of Chakravarti with regard to direct cyclization of (XXXVIII) by carrying out a critical investigation following the lines developed by Chakravarti in fixing up the position of cyclization by alkylation.

As regards the deactivating influence of an alkyl group on an adjacent reactive methylene group as established above, it may be noted that an alkyl group does not deactivate the methylene group to such an extent as to make it wholly unsuitable for Dieckmann cyclization. For instance, as was observed by Chakravarti¹⁷, ethyl 1,4-dimethylpentane-1,3,5-tricarboxylate (XLV) on Dieckmann cyclization smoothly yields ethyl 3,6-dimethylcyclohexan-1-one-2,4-dicarboxylate (XLVI). In this case, the α -methylene group, although partially deactivated by the methyl group in the β -position, is sufficiently active to take part in the cyclization. Consequently, ring closure proceeds through the α -methylene group as there is no other alternative way for the cyclization of this tricarboxylic ester with sodium.

As a result of a critical survey of the results on the course of cyclization of polycarboxylic esters with sodium according to Dieckmann, it has been possible to arrive at the following conclusions by Chakravarti^{23,33}. These are also in accord with the results obtained in the cyclization of other similar esters as carried out by other workers (cf. Biswas³⁴).

(i) The action of sodium on the ester of a β -alkyl -adipic or -pimelic acid, having two alternatives for cyclization, may be expected to lead to a ketonic ester in which the reactive methylene group, nearer to the alkyl radical remains unaffected by preference.

30. N. N. Chatterjee, B. K. Das and G. N. Barpujari. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 161.

31. R. N. Chakravarti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1315.

32. K. Sen and P. Bagchi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 1125.

33. R. N. Chakravarti, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1960, 26A (Suppl. I), 48.

34. R. N. Biswas, *Science and Culture*, 1963, 29, 51.

The other isomer in such a case, if produced at all, can only be in much smaller amount.

(ii) In the case of a β -carbethoxy-adipic or -pimelic ester, having two alternatives for cyclization, the product of sodium condensation usually leads to a mixture of the two isomeric keto-esters in which the keto-ester formed by interaction of the α -methylene group with the carbethoxy group at the other end of the chain predominates.

(iii) In the case of the ester of a β -alkyl-adipic or -pimelic acid, in which the α -methylene group is the only methylene group present in the molecule adjacent to a carbethoxy group and suitable for the cyclization, the sodium condensation proceeds smoothly in spite of the deactivating influence of the alkyl group.

(iv) The deactivating influence of the alkyl group on the adjacent methylene group appears to be due to its strong electron releasing properties.

(v) In the case of an adipic or pimelic ester having both an alkyl group and a carboalkoxy group attached to the β -carbon atom, the effect of the alkyl group predominates, and the α -methylene group of the starting ester remains intact in the cyclized product by preference if there is the other possibility for the cyclization of the ester through the reactive methylene group near the other end of the chain.

(vi) As the effect of deactivation of a methylene group by an adjacent alkyl group is much more pronounced than the activating influence of a carboalkoxy group on the adjacent methylene group, it is inferred that quantitatively the positive or electron releasing character of an alkyl group is much greater than the negative or electron accepting character of a carboalkoxy group.

More recently, Chakravarti and Dutta³⁵⁻³⁸ studied critically the cyclization of ethyl pentane-3-acetate-1,3-dicarboxylate (XLVII, R = Et) (Chart VIII) which is the ethyl analogue, in place of methyl, of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I). Exactly the same procedure was adopted in this investigation by pinpointing the methylene group through which the cyclization takes place by taking recourse to alkylation of the Dieckmann cyclization product. In other words, this tricarboxylic ester was cyclized in the usual way with sodium and then the cyclized sodio-salt was methylated *in situ* with methyl iodide. The methylated product was subjected to acid hydrolysis to the tricarboxylic acid (XLVIII, R = Et) and/or (XLIX, R = Et), as also to ketonic hydrolysis to the keto-acid (L, R = Et), and/or (LI, R = Et). Authentic specimens of the tricarboxylic acids (XLVIII, R = Et) and (XLIX, R = Et), and the keto-acids (L, R = Et) and (LI, R = Et) were synthesized by direct and unambiguous methods. From a comparison of these with the corresponding products obtained by acid and ketonic hydrolysis of the cyclized methylated product of (XLVII, R = Et) it was observed that in line with the previous findings this cyclization proceeded through the methylene group in the δ -position, with the α -methylene group remaining unaffected. Thus in this case also the methylene group in the α -position was found

35. R. N. Chakravarti and N. Dutta, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 22.

36. R. N. Chakravarti and N. Dutta, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 62.

37. R. N. Chakravarti and N. Dutta, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 113.

38. R. N. Chakravarti and N. Dutta, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1964, 12, 165.

to be much less reactive due to the ethyl group attached to the β -carbon atom of (XLVII). The negative effect of the carboxy group attached to the β -carbon atom is not much appreciable as compared to the positive effect of the ethyl group.

It may also be mentioned that the case of cyclization of ethyl hexane-3-acetate-1,3-dicarboxylate (XLVII, R = *n*-Pr) was also studied critically along the same lines as above by Chakravarti and Dutta³⁹⁻⁴¹. In this case also in agreement with the findings of Chakravarti, the cyclization takes place through the methylene group in the δ -position and not appreciably through the α -methylene group, which is adjacent to the *n*-Pr group attached to the β -carbon atom of (XLVII, R = *n*-Pr).

A re-examination of the structure of the product of cyclization of ethyl 2-methylbutane-1,2,4-tricarboxylate (I) was undertaken more recently by Chakravarti and Dutta⁴² on the basis of physical data. For this purpose, methyl esters of 2,3-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (Product A) (as XVII, R = Me), 2,4-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic acid (Product B) (as XVIII, R = Me), and of methylester of product of hydrolysis of Dieckmann cyclization of (I) and *in situ* methylation (Product D) were studied. The I.R. spectra of these were determined as film. It was observed that a number of peaks are common in all the three spectra, but in some of the others, Product B and Product D have identical peaks where as the corresponding peaks of Product A are some what shifted in position. In view of this it may be inferred that Product D consists at least for the major part of Product B, but it is difficult to draw any conclusion as to the presence or absence of small amounts of Product A in Product D.

39. R. N. Chakravarti and N. Dutta, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1966, 14, 15.

40. R. N. Chakravarti and N. Dutta, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1967, 15, 61.

41. R. N. Chakravarti and N. Dutta, *Bull. Calcutta School Trop. Med.*, 1967, 15, 99.

42. N. Dutta, D. Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, May, 1966.

It is to be noted that Products A and B are each capable of existing in two stereoisomeric forms, Product A—(LII) and (LIII); Product B—(LIV) and (LV).

Chart IX

Gas liquid chromatography of product A and product B showed two peaks each indicating presence of two isomers in each case as in Chart IX. GLC of Product D, on the other hand, showed three peaks two of which are strong ones and correspond to those of Product B. The third peak is a very weak one and corresponds to one of the peaks due to Product A. The other peak due to Product A being a very weak one is overlapped by one of the peaks due to Product B. From a study of the GLC it appears that Product D consists of Product B to the extent of 90–95% and about 5% of Product A.

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